

Role of the Teacher and School in the Context of Development of “Education for Peace”

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Abstract

In the current global perspective, the concept of education for peace is a sign of an epoch-making change. All the ventures and works being done in the world have the same aim - peace. Where there is peace there is growth, where there is growth there is happiness and where there is happiness there is humanity. The present society needs to be oriented towards peace rather than violence. Our way of life should be guided by the discipline of peace and education can do this work in the right way. If the education for peace is summed up, then it can be said that the education of peace is an essential condition of today's education. Education for peace is really education for life and its purpose is to develop such values, skills and methods etc. among the people so that they can behave cordially with others and become responsible citizens.

Key words- *Education for Peace, Peace, Human Rights, Sustainable Development, Life Skills, Culture of Peace, Conflict Management.*

Education for Peace: An Introduction

The concept of education for peace marks an epoch-making change. Education for peace is a medium and idea to establish non-violence through education in the whole world and its aim is not only to establish peace between humans and nations but also to keep it lasting. Education for peace is different from 'peace-education'. The status of 'peace' in 'Peace-Education' is like a subject included in the curriculum; whereas on the other hand, the way we are talking about peace in

“Education for Peace”, in that form, it emerges as a vision for shaping education. This is a sign of an epoch-making change in the process of exchange of education. Presently the enterprise of education is controlled by market forces. Education for Peace does not abstain from the market, but it does not see the market as the object of education. Market is just a part of our life-world. Education for Peace is education for life and it is not merely training for a living, but it aims at equipping people with values, skills and attitudes that will enable them to become full individuals and

responsible citizens who are cordial with others.

Historically, moral education and value education are the ancestors of education for peace. They have quite a few in common. According to the National Curriculum Framework for School Education, 2000, religion is a source of value-creation. Values and attitudes are the building blocks of a culture of peace. Then what is the specialty of education for peace? Why should we bother ourselves and the children (students) by carrying the burden of a new approach? Education for Peace talks about significantly reducing the burden of studies, not increasing it. Peace embodies the joy of life. From the perspective of peace, learning should be a pleasurable experience and happiness is the essence of life. Education for peace also includes value-education, but the two are not the same. Peace is a relevant and useful pedagogical point for the coherence of values. Peace gives concrete shape to the aims of values and inspires their internalization. Two main implications for education for peace have been recognized as holistic drivers. These implications are-

1. Peace encompasses all aspects and dimensions of human existence in an interdependent manner. Those who are at peace with themselves can, at the same time, behave peacefully with others and develop the sensitivity that is necessary for a proper and

loving attitude towards nature. Spiritual and psychological peace would be neither fertile nor sustainable without social, economic and ecological peace.

2. Reciprocity is inherent in peace. Values like love, freedom and peace can only be nurtured by sharing it among others. Their prosperity lies only in sharing them. If one desires such extravagant peace in which there is no room for the peace of others, then he is a victim of a dangerous deception. The aims of education for such peace are two fold – (a) empowering people to choose the path of peace rather than violence, and (b) making them the originator of peace rather than the consumer. In this sense, education for peace is an essential component of holistic basic education, which aims at holistic development of the individual. Teacher and school have a special and important role in the development of education for peace, which can be presented as follows-

Role of the Teacher in the context of Education for Peace

The role of the teacher in the context of education for peace can be summed up as follows:

1. In the context of education for peace, the teacher should inculcate values related to the development of education for peace in the classroom; For example, love, tolerance, caring, understanding, interdependence, compassion, harmony,

- empathy, spirituality, righteousness, gratitude and gratitude etc.
2. Schools are nurseries of education for peace and in these nurseries by the teachers, children's trees related to education for peace are prepared; as trees make the environment pure or provide purity; In the same way, they prepare children's trees related to education for peace. Children propagate peace in the world, that is, they establish an atmosphere of peace in the society.
 3. In the context of education for peace, the teacher's first responsibility is to help the students to become a good person and citizen, to encourage them to make full use of their abilities, not only in their interest but also for the betterment of the society.
 4. In the context of education for peace, the teacher can be compared to the gardener who is the seed of knowledge and good values, who waters it with the water of his compassion and motherhood and removes the weeds of ignorance.
 5. The role of the teacher in the context of education for peace can also be expressed in the context that good teachers are ideals of peace values, they have the art of listening, the humility to recognize and correct mistakes, and they share with their peers. Take responsibility for the work done by each other, share concerns and solve each other's problems beyond differences.
 6. In the context of education for peace, a major responsibility and duty of the teacher is to make the classroom environment positive in terms of teaching-learning process and at the same time, he should ensure such an environment in the classroom so that the classroom A proper environment or environment can be established in the context of education for peace.
 7. It is absolutely necessary for a teacher in the context of education for peace that he should have an inclination towards peace and he does not propagate violence unknowingly.
 8. In the context of imparting education for peace, during the teaching-learning process, the teacher should ensure or ensure that the methods and techniques he is using in the classroom in the context of teaching-learning process It should be the one who enhances education for peace and it should pave the way for the education of peace.
 9. Teacher's ability to differentiate between facts, ideas and beliefs, recognize discrimination and prejudice, pre-information and issues and problems contained in reasoning and debate in the classroom in the context of education for

peace, correctly Presentation of reasoning etc. should also be included.

10. In the context of education for peace, the teacher should also ensure in the context of the classroom that the student can stay away from the problem, recognize or understand the main part or part of it, raise his/her level of thinking and avoid any problem. A special strategy can be devised to deal with the particular situation.
11. Apart from this, in the context of education, the teacher should make all those efforts directly and indirectly which are necessary for education for peace and which can be used easily in practical and daily life.

Role of the School in the context of Education for Peace

The role of the school in the context of education for peace can be presented or expressed as follows:

1. Various types of stories, episodes, incidents and discussions etc. should be encouraged by the school to increase tolerance and understanding in the context of education for peace among the students.
2. In the context of education for peace, various types of social and national festivals should be celebrated by the school and through them the concept of

education for peace should be established and developed.

3. In the context of education for peace, proper development of values related to the development of education for peace should be done by the school from time to time so that by adopting these values, the path of education for peace can be paved and the society can A new direction and basis can be provided.
4. An important suggestion and argument related to the role of school in the context of education for peace can also be presented that different types of national and international days should be organized by schools: Human Rights Day, United Nations Day, Environment Day, Disabled Day and Peace Day etc. and proper participation of students should also be ensured in them. When such events will be organized by the school, then the proper path will be paved for the development of education for peace at the global level among the students.
5. In the context of education for peace, peace building skills can be developed in students by including peace in organizing various types of seminars and programs.
6. In the context of the development of education for peace by the school, children should be made sensitive and responsible towards each other and proper development of the spirit of world

brotherhood, world welfare and world peace should be done in them.

7. In the context of this education, activities and programs related to role play, creation of peace poems and stories, organizing plays related to peace and composing peace songs etc. can also be organized by the school to ensure the participation of children.
8. In the context of education for peace, peace and unity camps should also be organized by the school from time to time to promote and spread the message of education for peace.
9. Key peace skills related to education for peace should also be developed in the students by the school from time to time or during prayer meetings. In these skills, special attention should be given to communication skills, thinking skills and personal skills.
10. In addition to the above, some of the main principles related to education for peace should also be used in the context of school life and teaching-learning process in spreading and developing the concept of education for peace by the school. At the same time, various principles related to peace should also be incorporated in the school life and environment; Such as the principle of peace building and establishment, the principle of conflict management and change, the principle of

civic education, the principle of democracy and justice, the principle of morality and values, the principle of life skills and personal welfare, the principle of human rights and sustainable development, etc. If it is properly incorporated in the school life, then it can be said with certainty that the development of education for peace can be done very easily in the students, etc.

Some major tips and recommendations regarding Education for Peace

Some of the major suggestions and recommendations in the context of education for peace are as follows, which we can apply in practical and daily life in the context of development of education for peace-

- Education for peace should be kept as a whole in the context of school curriculum formulation and development.
- In the context of education for peace, supplementary curriculum should be prepared related to the promotion of peace values and skills, as well as the establishment of peace clubs and libraries in schools.
- At each stage of the teacher education program, special importance should be given to education for peace within the accepted goal of education.
- Training programs and workshops should be organized for teachers and parents in

- the context of imparting education for peace and its practical and daily use.
- Volunteer role should be played by teachers and students in peace projects and programs run by various types of non-governmental organizations and institutions and the work related to them should be done.
 - To make the school environment conducive to education for peace, it should be kept away from all forms of violence.
 - A manual on the causes and measures of violence in schools in the context of education for peace should be prepared and made available to all teachers and students and instructions should be given in the manual as to what are the types of violence and how to avoid them. How it can be dealt with.
 - For peace in school life, practical steps should be taken in the context of promoting the culture of peace in the context of education and special cooperation of society and other organizations should be taken in this.
 - An agency should be established in the context of education for peace at the state and district level and for monitoring the education for peace, especially in textbook writing, teacher education, classroom education and school system, necessary and required changes and reforms should be made.
 - In the context of education for peace, mutual exchange programs should be organized among the students of different streams and they should be freed from special types of prejudices, regional, caste and class barriers.
 - Media should be included as a partner and assistant in the context of education for peace and to promote values related to peace films, pictures and other types of materials etc. should be collected and displayed or distributed in school and society.
 - Involve the media as a participant and facilitator in the education context for peace and to collect films, pictures and other types of materials etc. to promote values related to peace and they should be displayed and distributed in the school and society.
 - Students, parents and teachers should be encouraged to adopt a calm attitude towards the problems and disputes arising in the school and classroom and in this context the parent-teacher relationship should be strengthened.
 - Education for peace should be used as a special tool in the context of education to be given in the future or in the context of education review or policy and for teachers to be organized in the context of education for peace. Education for peace

should be included seriously in the orientation and training activities.

Conclusion- Based on the above analysis, it can be said that education for peace is education for life and its main objective is to equip people with such values, skills and attitudes so that they can behave cordially with others and be responsible. To become a citizen in the context of education for peace and its development, the teacher can play an important role and this role depends on his own personality and behaviour. If the teacher embodies the teaching-learning work and process as the basis of education for peace, then it can be said with certainty that the teacher has a special and remarkable contribution in education for peace; on the other hand, if we discuss the role of school in the context of education for peace, then it can be said that school is the medium or means by which education for peace can be implemented. All those tasks and activities etc. given in the above can be done by the school which promote education for peace and at the same time provide a new basis to it. Along with the school, the teacher can also play an important role to make education for peace in practical and daily life. Peace starts from the individual and goes to the family, community, nation and global village; therefore, in the context of education for peace, a strategy should be devised by the school and the teacher to promote the culture of peace so that not only the teaching-learning process can

go on smoothly; Rather, wide publicity can be done in the context of education for peace within the school and society as well.

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